

FORMULATION AND IN VITRO EVALUATION OF BILAYER TABLET FOR THE TREATMENT OF HYPERTENSION AND DIABETES

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ABSTRACT

In the present work bi-layer tablet of Aliskiren and Empagliflozin were prepared by wet granulation method. Using superdisintegrants such as sodium starch glycolate and croscarmellose for immediate release layer and for sustained release layer polymer like HPMC K4M and HPMC K100M was used. Best formulation of each layer were selected for bi-layer tablet and bilayer tablet were prepared. Bi-layered tablets were subjected to hardness, weight variation, friability, drug content uniformity, in vitro drug release and drug polymer interaction. The above studies led to following: FTIR studies indicate that the drug is compatible with all the excipients. Both immediate and sustained release layer were prepared by wet granulation method. The prepared tablet of both layer were evaluated for pure and post compression parameters.

The stability research revealed that after three months, the tablets had not changed much. The produced bilayered tablets using superdisintegrants, release retardant polymers, and various excipients were able to display all the characteristics of a Bilayered tablet, according to the observations.

KEYWORDS: Bilayer tablet, Hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

The most popular method of administering medication is orally. Patients and doctors prefer tablets as the best oral dosing type. A bilayer tablet is useful for the sequential release of two

medications in tandem, with one layer providing sustained release and Immediate release is an additional layer.¹ Bilayer tablets offer several significant advantages over control tablets with a single layer.

For instance, by combining layers with distinct release patterns or by mixing slowrelease and immediate - release layers, these tablets which are frequently used to prevent bilayer tablets have made it possible to design controlled drug delivery with predetermined release profiles.

Conventional dose forms typically result in significant variations in the drug's concentration in the bloodstream and tissues, which can lead to unwanted toxicity and ineffectiveness.

The idea of regulated drug delivery systems was inspired by factors including inconsistent absorption and repeated doses.

By localizing the medication at the site of action, lowering the necessary dose, or ensuring consistent drug delivery, sustained or controlled delivery systems aim to either decrease the frequency of dosing or increase the drug's effectiveness.

Ensuring patient compliance and improving medication efficacy are the main goals of sustained release drug administration.

By physically separating APIs, bilayer tablets can prevent chemical incompatibilities and allow for the creation of distinct drug release patterns (immediate release with prolonged release) Bilayer tablets can separate two incompatible substances and be used for the sequential release of two medications in combination. They can also be used for sustained release tablets, where the first layer is immediately released as the initial dose and the second layer is the maintenance dose.

Both rapid and sustained release layers are present in bilayer tablets. The first dose is administered by the quick release layer. It has superdisintegrants that accelerate the rate of drug release and achieve a rapid onset of effect (loading dose), while the sustained release (maintenance dose) layer delivers the drug over an extended period of time.

The most common chronic noncommunicable diseases and multifactorial disorders impacting both developed and emerging nations are type 2 diabetes mellitus and hypertension. countries.

Diabetes mellitus and hypertension are mostly caused by hereditary and lifestyle factors. Over the past three decades, the prevalence of type 2 diabetes has increased from 1.2% to 11%.

Patients with type 2 diabetes are two to four times more likely to die from cardiovascular causes than those without the disease.

Heart disease is the most frequent cause of death for diabetic patients. Additionally, amputations, blindness, endstage renal disease, and peripheral vascular disease are common comorbidities in diabetes individuals.

Therefore, combination therapy is crucial for preventing diabetes in hypertensive patients. One of the main dangers associated with heart disease is hypertension.

Figure 1: Bilayer Tablet.

The primary cause of stroke is hypertension, which is also a significant risk factor for myocardial infarction, sudden cardiac death, coronary artery disease, and its consequences.

The prevalence of hypertension increases with age; for instance, approximately 50% of individuals between the ages of 60 and 69 have hypertension, and the prevalence increases further above the age of 70. Nevertheless, it is well known that several potential cardiovascular drug molecules have bioavailability problems related to acid instability, enzymatic degradation, and low water solubility, which could lead to inconsistent and insufficient oral absorption.

Due to their significant first pass metabolism and short duration of action, they also have a short half-life. As a result, they must be administered repeatedly, which is uncomfortable for the elderly population.

High blood glucose is the hallmark of diabetes mellitus, a chronic metabolic disease. Hyperglycemia in concentration. Diabetes mellitus comes in two varieties. Insulin is used to manage type-1 diabetes.

Treatment for type 2 diabetes starts with nutrition, but oral hypoglycemic medications are frequently required. Oral antidiabetic medications come in several different kinds.

When using medication to treat any illness, the best dosing schedule is one that swiftly reaches and maintains the targeted therapeutic drug concentration in plasma. consistent during the entire course of treatment.

One of the major dangers associated with heart disease is hypertension. Although it is a significant risk factor for cardiovascular death and morbidity, it is not a disease in and of itself.

The primary cause of stroke, a significant risk factor for coronary artery disease, and its aftereffects, myocardial infarction, and unexpected cardiac death. The bilayer tablet will be ready to show the various ways that pharmaceuticals work in a single system.

Aliskiren is an immediate release medication, while empagliflozin is a sustained release medication. distinct advantages of combination therapy over monotherapy include the reduction of dose-dependent adverse effects, the elimination of dose-related danger by a low-dose combination of two distinct drugs, The clinical and metabolic effects that result from the maximum dosage of each component of the combined tablet are minimized when two separate medications are used in low dosages. The inclusion of one agent may counteract some of the negative effects of the other.

Therefore, the goal of the current effort is to develop and assess bilayer tablets of antihypertensive and antidiabetic medications for better disease management, to lessen side effects, and to increase patient compliance.

The necessity of a bilayer tablet

1. To administer fixed dose combinations of various APIs, extend the life cycle of drug products, create novel drug delivery systems such chewing devices and floating tablets for gastroretentive drug delivery, and extend the buccal/mucoadhesive delivery system
2. To create a swellable or erodible barrier for release, the overall surface area available for the API layer can be altered by sandwiching with one or two inactive layers.
3. To control the release of API from one layer by separating incompatible active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) from one another using the functional property of another layer (e.g., osmotic property).
4. Managing the pace at which one or two distinct active medicinal substances are delivered.

Advantages

1. Stable and economical (chemical & microbiological)
2. Taste and odor can be covered with a coating.
3. Precise and consistent dosage.
4. Generally easy to swallow.
5. Prevents medication interactions.
6. Enables both quick and continuous release of drugs.

Disadvantages

1. A reduced yield of production.
2. Inadequate control over the weight of each layer.
3. Children and unconscious individuals may find it difficult to swallow.
4. Certain medications are challenging to compress.
5. Drugs with poor solubility or dissolution may have reduced bioavailability.

Types of Bilayer Tablets

- a. Homogeneous: Same drug, different release patterns (immediate + extended).
- b. Heterogeneous: Different drugs or incompatible substances.

Tablet Press Types

1. Single-sided press
 - a. Simple, low cost.

b. Limitations: poor weight control, weak layer separation, quality issues.

2. Double-sided press

- a. Better control and precision.
- b. Uses compression force monitoring.
- c. Limitation: requires higher compression force.

Different Methods for Bi-layer Tablets

A) OROS pulls technology

This system is mostly composed of two or three levels, of which one or more are drugessential layers and the remaining layers are push layers.

The medication and two or more distinct agents make up the majority of the drug layer.

Thus, the drugs in this drug layer are weakly soluble. Osmotic and suspending agents are also added. The tablet is encased in a semi-permeable membrane.

Figure 2: OROS push pull technology.

B) EN SO TROL Technology

EShore Laboratory uses an integrated strategy to drug delivery that focuses on identifying and incorporating the identified enhancer into controlled release technologies in order to improve solubility by an order of magnitude or to generate an optimal dose form.

Figure 3: EN SO TROL Technology.

C) DUREDASTM Technology

The Dual Release Drug Delivery technology from Elan Drug Technologies is another name for this technology.

DUREDAS TM Technology is a bilayer tablet that can deliver two medications at varying rates of release in a single dosage form, or it can give rapid or sustained release of two pharmaceuticals.

Within a single tablet, the tableting technique can produce both a modified release hydrophilic matrix complex and an instant granulate.

A mixture of hydrophilic polymers gives the dosage form its modified-release characteristics.

D) DUROS Technology

An exterior cylindrical titanium alloy reservoir makes up the system. This reservoir shields the drug molecules from enzymes and has a high impact strength. The DUROS technology is a tiny medicine dispensing device that functions similarly to a tiny needle and continuously releases a little amount of concentrated form over the course of several months or a year.

Figure 4: DUROS Technology.

Basic Formulation Steps

1. Fill first layer
2. Compress first layer
3. Remove upper punch
4. Fill second layer
5. Final compression

Figure 5: Compression steps of bilayer tablet.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIAL

Sr. No.	Name of Chemical	Name of Supplier
1	Aliskiren	Ajanta pharma limited, Mumbai
2	Empagliflozin	Ajanta pharma limited, Mumbai
3	Lactose	SBSPM Pharmacy College, Ambajogai
4	HPMC K4M	SBSPM Pharmacy College, Ambajogai
5	HPMC K100M	SBSPM Pharmacy College, Ambajogai
6	Microcrystalline cellulose	SBSPM Pharmacy College, Ambajogai
7	PVP K-30	SBSPM Pharmacy College, Ambajogai
8	Magnesium stearate	SBSPM Pharmacy College, Ambajogai
9	Talc	SBSPM Pharmacy College, Ambajogai
10	Croscarmellose sodium	SBSPM Pharmacy College, Ambajogai
11	Sodium Starch glycolate	SBSPM Pharmacy College, Ambajogai

METHODS

Pre-Formulation & Evaluation

1. Pre-formulation Studies

First step in dosage form development.

Focus: physicochemical properties of drug & excipients.

Aim: Ensure stable, safe, and effective formulation.

Melting point: Melting point of the Aliskiren and Empagliflozin were determined by capillary method in triplicate

Solubility: Tested in water, methanol, alcohol, isopropyl alcohol.

λ_{max} determination: Drugs scanned (200–400 nm) using UV spectrophotometer.

Empagliflozin: ~224 nm

Aliskiren: ~279 nm

Calibration Curves

Calibration Curve for Empagliflozin

The initial stock solution was made by precisely weighing 100 mg of empagliflozin and dissolving it in 100 ml of phosphate buffer 6.8. To create the II stock solution, 10 ml of the aforementioned solution was diluted to 100 ml using the same solvent. To obtain 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 µg/ml of the final solution, the aliquot amount of II stock solution was further diluted. The calibration curve was shown as concentration against absorbance across the range of 5–30 µg/mL with correlation after the absorbance was measured in the appropriate solvents against 224 nm.

Calibration Curve for Aliskiren

The initial stock solution was made by precisely weighing 100 mg of Aliskiren and dissolving it in 100 ml of 0.1 N HCl.

To create the II stock solution, 10 ml of the aforementioned solution was diluted to 100 ml using the same solvent.

To obtain 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 µg/ml of the final solution, the aliquot amount of II stock solution was further diluted.

The calibration curve was plotted as concentration against absorbance over the range of 5-30 µg/mL with correlation after the absorbance was measured in the appropriate solvents against 279nm.

Physical Characterization: Loss on Drying (LOD) Measures moisture content.

$$\% \text{ LOD} = (W2-W3) / (W2-W1) \times 100$$

Where, W1 = Weight of empty weighing bottle

W2 = Weight of weighing bottle + sample

W3 = Weight of weighing bottle + dried sample

Drug–Excipient Compatibility

Ensures no interaction affecting stability.

METHODS

Storage study: 40°C / 75% RH (accelerated) 4°C (control)

FT-IR Spectroscopy: Detects interaction via peak shifts (4000–400 cm⁻¹).

Angle of Repose

The funnel method was used to calculate the granules' angle of repose.

The funnel was placed on a burette stand at a specific height of 2.5 cm.

After passing the powder sample through the funnel, a pile was formed.

Granules were prevented from being added as soon as the pile reached the funnel's tip.

Without upsetting the pile, a circle was drawn across it.

The pile's radius was recorded.

The average value was obtained when the identical process was carried out three times.

The following formula was used to get the angle of repose:

$$\tan \theta = h/r \text{ (or) } \theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$$

Where, h and r are the height and radius of the powder cone.

Table 1: Angle of repose as an indication of granule flow properties.

Angle of repose (°)	Type of flow
<25	Excellent
25-30	Good
30-40	Poor
>40	Very poor

Bulk Density

Weigh the dry granules precisely into a graduated 100 ml measuring cylinder, record the volume, and use the formula to get the bulk density.

Bulk density is calculated by dividing the raw powder's weight by its volume.

Tapped Density

A graduated 100 ml measuring cylinder filled with a known mass of dry granules was used to determine it.

To achieve a constant volume of powder bed, the cylinder was allowed to fall under its own weight onto a hard surface from a height of 10 cm every second for 100 taps.

Tapped Density = Weight of the tapped powder / Volume of the tapped powder.

Carr's Index

The flow property of the granules was determined by % Carr's Index.

it was calculated by the following formula.

$$\text{Carr's Index} = \frac{\text{Tapped Density} - \text{Bulk Density}}{\text{Tapped Density}} \times 100$$

Table 2: Carr's index as an indication of granule flow prope.

Carr's Index (%)	Type of flow
5 –15	Excellent
12 – 16	Good
18 – 21	Fair to Possible
23 -35	Poor
33-38	Very Poor

Hausner's Ratio

Flow property Hausner's Ration is an indication of flowability of the granules. It was calculated by following formula. Hausner's Ratio = Tapped Density /Bulk Density.

Table 3: Hausner's ratio as an indication of granule flow properties.

Flow character	Hausner's ratio
Excellent	1.00-1.11
Good	1.12-1.18
Fair	1.19-1.25
Possible	1.26-1.34
Poor	1.35- 1.45
Very Poor	1.46 - 1.59
Very very Poor	>1.60

Formulation of Bilayer Tablets**Immediate Release Layer (Aliskiren)**

Using the formulas listed in Table 14, Aliskiren and sodium starch glycolate were blended uniformly using PVP K30 as a binder to create the immediate release granules utilizing the wet granulation process. After passing the cohesive material through a sieve #20, it was dried at 60 °C for an hour, yielding a moisture level of 12%, as measured by an IR moisture balance.

Table 4: Formulation of immediate release layer.

Sr. No.	Ingredients	AF1	AF2	AF3	AF4	AF5	AF6
		(mg)	(mg)	(mg)	(mg)	(mg)	(mg)
1	Aliskiren	50	50	50	50	50	50
2	Lactose	82	79.5	82	79.5	77	77
3	Croscarmellose sodium	10	12.5	-	-	5	10
4	Sodium starch glycolate	-	-	10	12.5	10	5
5	Microcrystalline cellulose	35	35	35	35	35	35
6	PVP K-30	5	5	5	5	5	5
7	Magnesium stearate	10	10	10	10	10	10
8	Talc	8	8	8	8	8	8
Total	(mg)	200	200	200	200	200	200

Formulation of the sustained release layer.

Table 5: Formulation of sustained release layer.

Sr No.	Ingredients	EF1	EF2	EF3	EF4	EF5	EF6
		(mg)	(mg)	(mg)	(mg)	(mg)	(mg)
1	Empagliflozin	120	120	120	120	120	120
2	Lactose	52	44.50	37	52	44.50	37
3	HPMC K4M	45	52.5	60	-	-	-
4	HPMC K100M	-	-	-	45	52.5	60
5	Microcrystalline cellulose	60	60	60	60	60	60
6	PVP K-30	6	6	6	6	6	6
7	Magnesium stearate	8	8	8	8	8	8
8	Talc	9	9	9	9	9	9
	Total (mg)	300	300	300	300	300	300

Post compression Evaluation of Aliskiren and Empagliflozin

The tablets prepared were evaluated for the following parameters

Thickness, Weight variation, Hardness, Friability, Disintegration Time, Drug content, In-vitro Dissolution Studies, Stability Studies

Tablet Thickness

Thickness of the tablet is important for uniformity of tablet size. Thickness was measured using Vernier Callipers. It was determined by checking the thickness of ten tablets of each formulation. Vernier calliper consists of metric and imperial scales. The main metric scale is read first then read "hundredths of mm" of imperial scale (count the number of division until the lines coincides with the main metric scale. The imperial scale number is multiply with 0.02.

Weight Variation Test

Table no 6: IP standards of Uniformity of weight.

Sr. No.	Avg. Wt of Tablet (mg)	% of Deviation
1	Less than 80 mg	10
2	Less than 80 mg but more than 250 mg	7.5
3	more than 250 mg	5

Hardness

The hardness of each batch of tablet was checked by using Monsanto hardness tester.

The average hardness of 5 determinations was recorded.

Friability

10 tablets were weighed and the initial weight of these tablets was recorded and placed in Roche friabilator and rotated at the speed of 25 rpm for 100 revolutions. Percentage friability was calculated by

$$\% \text{ Friability} = \frac{\text{Initial wt} - \text{Final wt.}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

Disintegrating Time

The disintegration test is carried out in an apparatus containing a basket rack assembly with six glass tubes of 7.75 cm in length and 2.15 mm in diameter, the bottom of which consists of a #10 mesh sieve.

Drug Content

The tablets were crushed in a mortar and accurately weighed amount of average tablet weight was taken from the crushed blend and transferred in to a 100 mL volumetric flask.

Dissolution Studies

Empagliflozin (Sustained Release)

Medium: pH 6.8 buffer

Time: up to 20 hours

Speed: 45 rpm

Temp: 37°C

Aliskiren (Immediate Release)

Medium: 0.1 N HCl

Time: 45 min

Speed: 100 rpm

Bilayer Tablet Evaluation Dissolution in:

0.1 N HCl (initial 45 min)

pH 6.8 buffer (up to 24 hrs)

Drug Release Kinetics Models

Used to understand release mechanism:

1. Zero-order: Constant release
2. First-order: Concentration-dependent

3. Higuchi model: \sqrt{t} time dependent (matrix diffusion)
4. Korsmeyer–Peppas: Mechanism identification (n value)

Table 7: Mechanism of Drug Release as per Korsmeyer Equation/ Peppas's Model.

Sr.No.	'n' value	Drug Release
1	0.45	Fickian release
2	0.45 < n < 0.89	Non-Fickian release
3	0.89	Case II transport
4	Higher than 0.89	Super case II transport

Stability Studies

Conditions: 40°C / 75% RH (2–3 months)

Packaging: Aluminum foil, closed containers

Checked periodically for stability

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation Studies

1. Determination of λ_{\max}

λ_{\max} for Empagliflozin was Found at 224 nm.

λ_{\max} of Aliskiren was found to be 279 nm.

2. Solubility

It was determined as per procedure given in material and method part. The drug Empagliflozin is slightly soluble in water (pH 1-7.4), slightly soluble in ethanol, sparingly soluble in methanol.

The drug Aliskiren is soluble in water, slightly soluble in ethanol and soluble in methanol.

3. Determination of Melting Point

Table 8: Melting Point for Empagliflozin.

Test	Specification / Limit	Observations
Melting Point	151-153	152

Table 9: Melting Point for Aliskiren.

Test	Specification / Limit	Observations
Melting Point	98-99	98

Calibration Curve for Aliskiren

Table No. 10: Results for Aliskiren Linearity by UV Spectroscop.

Sr. No.	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
1	0	0
2	05	0.151
3	10	0.284
4	15	0.411
5	20	0.555
6	25	0.669
Correlation coefficient		0.9986

Figure No. 6: Calibration curve of Aliskiren by UV.

Calibration Curve of Empagliflozin

Table No. 11: Results for Empagliflozin by UV Spectroscopy.

Sr. No.	Concentration (ug/ml)	Absorbance
1	0	0
2	05	0.124
3	10	0.226
4	15	0.334
5	20	0.458
6	25	0.569
Correlation Coefficient		0.998

Figure No. 7: Calibration Curve for Empagliflozin by UV Spectroscopy.

Physical Characteristics

Loss on Drying

Table no. 12: Loss on Drying for Empagliflozin.

Test	Specification/ Limits	Observation
Loss on drying	Not more than 0.2%	0.1%

Table no. 13: Loss on Drying for Aliskiren.

Test	Specification/ Limits	Observation
Loss on drying	Not more than 0.2%	0.2%

Excipient Compatibility Studies Compatibility studies of Empagliflozin

The compatibility studies of the drugs with polymers are studies using FT-IR spectroscopy.

FT-IR Spectroscopy

The sample (drug and drug-excipient mixture in 1:1 ratio) in KBr (200-400mg) was compressed in to discs by applying a pressure of 5 tons for 5 min in hydraulic press.

Figure no. 8: IR Spectra of Aliskiren.

Figure no. 9: IR Spectrs of Empagliflozin.

Sr. no	Functional group	Wave no.(cm ⁻¹)
1	-NH stretch	3398
2	-OH stretch	3332
3	=C-H symmetric stretch	3041
4	-NH stretch Combination band	2062
5	-C=O stretching	1710
6	-C=C stretch ring	1444

Sr.no	Functional group	Wave no.(cm ⁻¹)
1	O-H stretching	3374
2	- Secondary NH stretching	3324
3	Aromatic C-H stretching	3011
4	Aliphatic C-H bending	2884
5	-C-N Stretching	1248
6	-C=O Stretching	1288

Figure no. 10: IR Spectra of Calcium Carbonate (Talc).

Sr.no	Functional group	Wave no.(cm ⁻¹)
1	-C=O stretching	1709
2	-C-O stretching	1229
3	=C-O Fingerprint	729

Figure no. 11: IR Spectra of Magnesium Stearate.

Sr.No	Functional group	Wave no.(cm ⁻¹)
1	Carboxylate stretching	2917 2850
2	COO- Asymmetric twin bands	1497 1477

Figure no. 12: IR Spectra of Micro Crystalline Cellulose.

Figure no. 13: IR Spectra of Croscamellose Glycolate.

Time	AIRF1	AIRF2	AIRF3	AIRF4	AIRF5	AIRF6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	14 ± 3.23	19 ± 3.47	22 ± 3.58	24 ± 27	26 ± 4.97	31 ± 3.89
10	21 ± 3.55	29 ± 3.30	33 ± 4.20	35 ± 3.30	41 ± 3.66	44 ± 3.64
15	37 ± 3.18	39 ± 4.55	45 ± 4.22	49 ± 4.11	55 ± 3.84	59 ± 3.84
20	49 ± 4.25	54 ± 4.61	59 ± 3.75	63 ± 4.63	67 ± 5.25	78 ± 4.33
25	58 ± 3.86	65 ± 3.78	66 ± 3.57	74 ± 4.98	80 ± 4.98	90 ± 3.87
30	67 ± 4.67	74 ± 3.79	77 ± 4.51	85 ± 4.87	97 ± 4.81	98 ± 3.55

Batch Code	Weight variation	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Friability (%)	Drug content (%)	Disintegration time (min)
AIRF1	200.9±1.5 8	5.96±0.06	2.86±0.03	0.75±0.0 8	98.11±1.1 8	3.40
AIRF2	201.2±1.6 1	4.19±0.11	2.90±0.09	0.59±0.0 3	97.64±1.8 1	3.44
AIRF3	199.8±1.6 1	6.36±0.04	2.89±0.06	0.57±0.0 5	98.64±1.2 7	3.09
AIRF4	199.7±2.00	6.18±0.08	2.86±0.02	0.66±0.0 4	99.60±0.9 3	3.25
AIRF5	201.1±2.53	4.15±0.05	2.91±0.05	0.64±0.0 2	99.42±1.3 1	3.65
AIRF6	200±1.82	4.54±0.12	2.88±0.08	0.70±0.0 3	99.50±1.8 0	2.54

EVALUATION OF PRE-COMPRESSION PARAMETERS

Flow properties: For Aliskiren Immediate release Layer

Table no. 13: Flow properties of Aliskiren Immediate release Layer.

Batch code	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Tapped density (g/cm ³)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose
AIRF1	0.536±0.001	0.626±0.004	12.611±0.218	1.136±0.031	19.495±0.355
AIRF2	0.575±0.004	0.646±0.005	15.085±0.227	1.172±0.019	18.371±0.276
AIRF3	0.554±0.005	0.625±0.004	15.772±0.108	1.165±0.023	19.422±0.174
AIRF4	0.684±0.002	0.683±0.002	13.898±0.176	1.154±0.015	16.246±0.155
AIRF5	0.611±0.009	0.583±0.008	11.766±0.205	1.142±0.008	17.914±0.040
AIRF6	0.655±0.003	0.756±0.007	11.147±0.156	1.123±0.026	17.102±0.078

For Empagliflozin Extended release Layer

Table no. 14: Flow properties of Empagliflozin Extended release Layer.

Batch code	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Tapped density (g/cm ³)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose
EERF2	0.560±0.007	0.688±0.001	14.485±0.329	1.168±0.018	18.461±0.064
EERF3	0.624±0.003	0.683±0.004	11.224±0.187	1.164±0.010	18.200±0.089
EERF4	0.644±0.006	0.704±0.002	16.530±0.126	1.233±0.011	22.547±0.279
EERF5	0.596±0.005	0.711±0.005	11.153±0.248	1.121±0.029	18.134±0.078
EERF6	0.594±0.005	0.728±0.003	12.117±0.398	1.257±0.030	18.187±0.103

POST-COMPRESSION EVALUATION PARAMETERS

Post Compression Evaluation of Aliskiren IR

Table no. 15: Post Compression Evaluation of Aliskiren IR.

Batch code	Weight variation	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Friability (%)	Drug content (%)	Disintegration time (min)
AIRF1	200.9±1.58	5.96±0.06	2.86±0.03	0.75±0.08	98.11±1.18	3.40
AIRF2	201.2±1.61	4.19±0.11	2.90±0.09	0.59±0.03	97.64±1.81	3.44
AIRF3	199.8±1.61	6.36±0.04	2.89±0.06	0.57±0.05	98.64±1.27	3.09
AIRF4	199.7±2.00	6.18±0.08	2.86±0.02	0.66±0.04	99.60±0.93	3.25
AIRF5	201.1±2.53	4.15±0.05	2.91±0.05	0.64±0.02	99.42±1.31	3.65
AIRF6	200±1.82	4.54±0.12	2.88±0.08	0.70±0.03	99.50±1.80	2.54

Table no. 16: In vitro drug release data of Aliskiren IR (AIRF1- AIRF6).

Time	AIRF1	AIRF2	AIRF3	AIRF4	AIRF5	AIRF6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	14 ± 3.23	19 ± 3.47	22 ± 3.58	24 ± 2.7	26 ± 4.97	31 ± 3.89
10	21 ± 3.55	29 ± 3.30	33 ± 4.20	35 ± 3.30	41 ± 3.66	44 ± 3.64
15	37 ± 3.18	39 ± 4.55	45 ± 4.22	49 ± 4.11	55 ± 3.84	59 ± 3.84
20	49 ± 4.25	54 ± 4.61	59 ± 3.75	63 ± 4.63	67 ± 5.25	78 ± 4.33
25	58 ± 3.86	65 ± 3.78	66 ± 3.57	74 ± 4.98	80 ± 4.98	90 ± 3.87
30	67 ± 4.67	74 ± 3.79	77 ± 4.51	85 ± 4.87	97 ± 4.81	98 ± 3.55

Figure No.14: In vitro drug release data of Aliskiren IR (AIRF1- AIRF6).

Post Compression Evaluation of Empagliflozin Extended release Layer

The results of all formulations were found to be within limits (weight variation 300.75-302.9, hardness range 4.34–6.24 kg/cm², friability <1%, drug content 97.42–99.37%, and all the values were reported in Table 29. In vitro drug release studies of extended release tablets were carried out using USP type II dissolution apparatus in 900 mL of 6.8 buffer solutions at 45 rpm up to 12 hr. The formulations EERF1-EERF6 showed drug release up to 99%. From that above data formulation EERF5 was optimized because drug release extended up to 12 Hr with maximum drug release. For bilayer tablet as it reflects good disintegration and dissolution.

Table no. 17: Post Compression Evaluation of Empagliflozin ER.

Batch code	Weight variation (%)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Friability(%)	Drug content (%)
EERF1	302.7±1.42	5.39±0.11	3.34±0.09	0.31±0.07	99.37±1.18
EERF2	302.9±2.30	4.34±0.03	3.30±0.14	0.36±0.03	98.60±1.02
EERF3	302.5±1.60	6.15±0.05	3.31±0.03	0.44±0.04	97.42±1.27
EERF4	301.85±1.15	6.24±0.07	3.28±0.05	0.37±0.03	98.56±0.84
EERF5	300.75±1.38	5.15±0.04	3.30±0.06	0.43±0.07	98.42±1.26
EERF6	302.40±1.32	4.53±0.03	3.33±0.03	0.49±0.03	97.62±0.60

Table no. 18: In vitro drug release data of Empagliflozin ER (EERF1-EERF6).

Time (hrs)	EERF1	EERF2	EERF3	EERF4	EERF5	EERF6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	10 ± 3.38	12 ± 3.65	13 ± 3.33	14 ± 3.97	12 ± 3.91	11 ± 3.25
2	19 ± 3.98	21 ± 3.37	19 ± 3.64	19 ± 3.65	16 ± 3.69	13 ± 3.63
3	27 ± 3.43	32 ± 4.25	29 ± 3.65	32 ± 3.77	28 ± 3.43	24 ± 4.01
4	38 ± 3.99	39 ± 3.83	39 ± 4.28	41 ± 3.23	35 ± 4.21	30 ± 4.25

5	49 ± 3.72	48 ± 3.54	47 ± 4.24	49 ± 3.62	43 ± 3.64	38 ± 3.45
6	59 ± 4.46	55 ± 3.68	55 ± 3.99	59 ± 3.84	56 ± 3.08	45 ± 3.23
7	66 ± 3.23	63 ± 3.59	59 ± 3.88	60 ± 4.10	56 ± 3.68	53 ± 3.64
8	79 ± 3.45	80 ± 4.37	72 ± 4.11	74 ± 3.5	63 ± 3.28	58 ± 4.21
9	86 ± 3.88	89 ± 3.47	83 ± 3.98	84 ± 4.13	80 ± 4.15	62 ± 3.82
10	99 ± 3.31	98 ± 3.98	97 ± 3.66	98 ± 3.98	84 ± 3.75	74 ± 4.30
11					95 ± 3.49	82 ± 4.16
12					99 ± 3.93	88 ± 4.43

Figure No. 15: In vitro drug release data of Empagliflozin ER (EERF1-EERF6).

EVALUATION OF BILAYER TABLETS

The prepared bilayer tablets were evaluated for post compression parameters and results were found to be within the limits mentioned in the above section. In vitro drug release studies of bilayer tablets were carried out using USP dissolution apparatus type II in 900 mL of 0.1 N HCl for first 30 minutes and in 900 mL of 6.8 phosphate buffer solution up to 12 hours. From the results, drug release of Aliskiren IR layer was found to be 98 % in 30 minutes and that of the Empagliflozin ER layer was 99 % at the end of 12 hours drug release of bilayer tablet.

Figure no. 16: IR Spectra of Bilayer Tablet.

Sr. no	Functional group	Wave no.(cm ⁻¹)
1	-OH stretch	3040
3	=C-H Aromatic stretch	3041
4	=C-H Stretching	2962 2934 2876
5	-C=O stretching Conjugated vinyl bond	1706
6	-C-S linkage stretching	772

Figure no. 17: Overlay Spectra of FTIR Spectrum.

Post-compression parameters for bi-layered tablet

Table no. 19: Post-compression parameters for bi-layered tablet.

Formulation	Weight variation Mean \pm SD	Hardness Mean \pm SD	Friability Mean \pm SD	Thickness Mean \pm SD	Drug content (%) Mean \pm SD
Bilayer Tablet	500.75 \pm 0.46	7.05 \pm 0.15	0.38 \pm 0.01	6.31 \pm 0.15	98.23 \pm 0.53

Figure No. 18: In vitro drug release data of from bilayer tablets.

Table no. 20: In vitro drug release data of from bilayer tablet.

Time (min)	Aliskiren (AIRF6)	Empagliflozin (EERF5)
	0.1 N HCl	% drug release
0	0	0
5	27 \pm 3.57	2 \pm 1.02
10	41 \pm 3.33	3 \pm 1.24

15	57± 3.6	4 ± 1.35
20	73± 5.11	5 ± 1.33
25	86± 2.77	6 ± 1.49
30	96 ± 3.73	7± 1.37
Time (hrs)	Phosphate buffer 6.8 solution	% drug release
1	-	9± 3.88
2	-	16 ± 4.67
3	-	26 ± 3.61
4	-	32 ± 4.49
5	-	44 ± 4.62
6	-	50 ± 3.55
7	-	54± 3.46
8	-	64 ± 2.26
9	-	80 ± 4.53
10	-	84 ± 3.63
11	-	95 ± 3.57
12	-	97 ± 3.31

Table no. 21: stability study data.

Stability period	40°C / 75% RH				
	Hardness Mean ± SD	% Friability Mean ± SD	% Drug content Mean ± SD	Drug release	
				IRL (30min)	SRL (720min)
Initial	7.04±0.68	0.39±0.0 2	98.22±0.533	99±4.7	96±3.33
1 month	7.06±0.50	0.46±0.0 7	98.04±0.752	99±7.7	95±4.33
2 month	6.49±0.46	0.54±0.0 6	97.95±0.793	97.8 ±4.9	96±3.33
3 month	5.84±0.51	0.64±0.0 5	96.43±0.922	99±5.4	96±3.33

The bi-layered tablets were subjected to short term stability study, storing the formulation at 40°C / 75% RH for 3 months. The data for stability studies revealed that no considerable differences in physical parameters, drug content and in vitro drug release rate were observed.

Figure 19: Immediate Release.

Figure 20: Bilayer Tablet.

Figure 21: Sustained Release.

CONCLUSION

utilizing super disintegrants such sodium starch glycolate and croscarmellose for the immediate release layer and polymers like HPMC K4M and HPMC K100M for the sustained release layer, bi-layered tablets containing aliskiren and empagliflozin were created in this study utilizing the wet granulation method.

For the purpose of creating a bilayered tablet, the best formulations of each layer were chosen. Hardness, weight fluctuation, friability, drug content homogeneity, in vitro drug release, and drug polymer interaction were all tested on bi-layered tablets.

The aforementioned research leads to the following findings

1. FTIR analyses showed that the medication is compatible with every excipient.

2. The wet granulation process was used to prepare the immediate and sustained release layers. Both layers' produced tablets were assessed for pre- and post-compression characteristics.
3. For the bi-layered tablet, one formulation of each layer was chosen based on the in vitro dissolution profile data. AIRF6 from formulations for quick release, as they displayed 98. percentage of medication release in 30 minutes. 99% drug release in 12 hours was demonstrated by EERF5 from the sustained release formulation.
4. The chosen immediate and sustained release layer was used to create the bilayer tablets.
5. It was discovered that the produced tablets have a hardness of 7.05 kg/cm.
6. The prepared tablet's friability was determined to be 1%.
7. All of the developed bi-layered tablet formulations had the same proportion medication content.
8. The bi-layered tablets' in vitro drug release pattern was identical to that of single-layer tablets.

The stability research revealed that after three months, the tablets had not changed much.

The produced bilayered tablets using superdisintegrants, release retardant polymers, and various excipients were able to display all the characteristics of a Bi-layered tablet, according to the observations.

REFERENCES

1. Prabakaran B, Elango K, Kumar KR, Jaison D. Formulation Development and Evaluation of Gastroretentive Bilayer Floating Tablets of Simvastatin and Telmisartan. *parameters*. 2016; 5(1): 9-18.
2. Deshpande RD, Gowda DV, Mahammed N, Maramwar DN. Bi-layer tablets-An emerging trend: a review. *International journal of pharmaceutical sciences and research*. 2011; 2(10): 2534-2544.
3. Ryakala H, Dineshmohan S, Ramesh A, Gupta VR. Formulation and in vitro evaluation of bilayer tablets of nebivolol hydrochloride and nateglinide for the treatment of diabetes and hypertension. *Journal of drug delivery*. 2015; 2015.
4. Chobanian AV, Bakris GL, Black HR, Cushman WC, Green LA, Izzo Jr JL, Jones DW, Materson BJ, Oparil S, Wright Jr JT, Roccella EJ. The seventh report of the joint national committee on prevention, detection, evaluation, and treatment of high blood pressure: the JNC 7 report. *Jama*., 2003; 289(19): 2560-2571.

5. Ghadi R, Garse H, Dand N, Kadam V, Waghmare N. Design and evaluation of novel bi-layered tablet for the effective treatment of hypertension. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2013; 3(12): 1530-1543.
6. Simão J, Chaudhary SA, Ribeiro AJ. Implementation of Quality by Design (QbD) for Development of Bilayer Tablets. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2023 Feb 22: 106412.
7. Han JK, Kim JY, Choi DH, Park ES. A formulation development strategy for dualrelease bilayer tablets: An integrated approach of quality by design and a placebo layer. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2022 Apr 25; 618: 121659.
8. Jin G, Ngo HV, Wang J, Cui JH, Cao QR, Park C, Jung M, Lee BJ. Design and evaluation of in vivo bioavailability in beagle dogs of bilayer tablet consisting of immediate release nanosuspension and sustained release layers of rebamipide. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2022 May 10; 619: 121718.
9. Soni A, Paprikar A, Lin S. Effect of alkalizing agent on abuse deterrent potential of multiple-unit ingestion of bilayer abuse-deterrent extended-release tablets using propranolol as model drug for opioids overdose crisis. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2021 May 1; 600: 120480.
10. Won DH, Park H, Ha ES, Kim HH, Jang SW, Kim MS. Optimization of bilayer tablet manufacturing process for fixed dose combination of sustained release high-dose drug and immediate release low-dose drug based on quality by design (QbD). *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2021 Aug 10; 605: 120838.
11. Maharjan A, Sun H, Cao Z, Li K, Liu J, Liu J, Xiao T, Peng G, Ji J, York P, Regmi B. Redefinition to bilayer osmotic pump tablets as subterranean river system within mini-earth via three-dimensional structure mechanism. *Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica B*. 2022 May 1; 12(5): 2568-77.
12. Akhtar M, Jamshaid M, Zaman M, Mirza AZ. Bilayer tablets: A developing novel drug delivery system. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*. 2020 Dec 1; 60: 102079.
13. Maddiboyina B, Hanumanaik M, Nakkala RK, Jhawar V, Rawat P, Alam A, Foudah AI, Alrobaian MM, Shukla R, Singh S, Kesharwani P. Formulation and evaluation of gastroretentive floating bilayer tablet for the treatment of hypertension. *Heliyon*. 2020 Nov 1; 6(11): e05459.

14. Lodha GS, Chemate SZ. Formulation and Evaluation of Teneiglipitin and Telmisartan Bilayer Tablets for the Treatment of Coexistent Type II Diabetes Mellitus and Hypertension. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*. 2019; 9(5): 26-38.
15. Sahoo BK, Pattajoshi SP, Pattajoshi S. Formulation and Evaluation of Bimolar Release of Ciprofloxacin HCl from Bilayer Gastro-Retentive Floating System. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2018; 8(2): 61-70.
16. Cheng L, Li T, Dong L, Wang X, Huo Q, Wang H, Jiang Z, Shan X, Pan W, Yang X. Design and evaluation of bilayer pump tablet of flurbiprofen solid dispersion for zero-order controlled delivery. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2018 May 1; 107(5): 1434-42.
17. Abbasi S, Yousefi G, Ansari AA, Mohammadi-Samani S. Formulation and in vitro evaluation of a fast-disintegrating/sustained dual release bucoadhesive bilayer tablet of captopril for treatment of hypertension crises. *Research in pharmaceutical sciences*. 2016 Jul; 11(4): 274.
18. Pujari PS, Uttekar PS, Chaudhari PD, Bamane PS. Formulation Development and Evaluation of Bilayer Floating Tablet of Antidiabetic Drugs. *Scholars Research Library Der Pharmacia Lettre*. 2016; 8(21): 34-54.
19. Pattanaik P, Patel KR. Formulation and In-Vitro Evaluation of Novel Fixed Dose Triple Combinations of Antidiabetic and Anti-Hypertensive Drugs for Treatment of Hypertension in Diabetic Patients. *Journal of pharmaceutical science and Bioscientificresearch.*, 2016; 6(6): 816823.
20. Ryakala H, Dineshmohan S, Ramesh A, Gupta VR. Formulation and in vitro evaluation of bilayer tablets of nebivolol hydrochloride and nateglinide for the treatment of diabetes and hypertension. *Journal of drug delivery*. 2015; 2015.
21. Ranpise N, Jamkar P, Langote H. Formulation and development of fixed dose combination of antihypertensive and antidiabetic agent for treatment of co-existent type two diabetes mellitus and hypertension. *Indian J. Pharm. Educ. Res.*, 2014; 48(1): 109-117.
22. Sharma SK, Mohan S, Jaimini M, Chauhan BS, Chatterjee A. Formulation and in-vitro evaluation of Bilayer tablets containing Pioglitazone HCl and Gliclazide for type II diabetes. *International Journal of PharmTech Research*, 2014; 6(2): 607-622.
23. Dey S, Mahanti B, Khila S, Mazumder B, Gupta SD. Formulation development and optimization of bilayer tablets of aceclofenac. *Expert opinion on drug delivery*, 2012 Sep 1; 9(9): 1041-50.